

Studies in Organo-arsenic Compounds. Part I.

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The physiological activity of azo and bisazo compounds have been shown to be dependent on the following factors: (1) presence of $-N=N-$, (2) the capability of liberating salicylic acid or its simple derivative due to decomposition, *e.g.*, Era chrome black or Chrysoamin, (3) presence of naphthalene nucleus which hastens the formation of skin, *e.g.*, Biebrich scarlets, Scarlet R, etc., and (4) for trypanocidal activity, the terminals joining the azo groupings must contain naphthalene nucleus with sulphonic and amino groups (Nicolle and Mesnil, *Ann. Inst. Pasteur.*, 1906, 20, 417).

It has also been found that the media in which the coupling takes place, play an important rôle so far as the trypanocidal activity is concerned. Thus the compounds obtained by coupling in acid medium, have very little or no action upon trypanosomes and if, however, the coupling is performed in alkaline solution, entirely different products are obtained leading almost invariably to the complete disappearance of the said bacillus.

The compounds containing naphthalene ring described in this paper, although they do not contain amino group, are expected to have enhanced trypanocidal activity due to the presence of arsenic in place of amino group. The coupling was done in alkaline media. The following are the additional considerations that may be put forward in favour of the new series of compounds. Modern researches on the diseases due to the parasitic organism, have pointed out clearly the reason why large number of synthetic drugs, very active from theoretical considerations, failed to bring about the expected result. The reason, assigned to the failure of such cases, is that these classes of compounds cannot penetrate into the actual seat of the organism on account of the absence of lipolytic action. The compounds described in the paper, are expected to have the lipolytic properties due to the presence of naphthyl sulphonic acid residue (Twitchell's reagent).

The compounds had all been prepared by diazotising the different aminocoumarins and coupling them in alkaline media with naph-

thylsulphoarsinic acid. This latter compound was prepared by Hill and Balls (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **44**, 2051) by sulphonating naphthylarsinic acid, but the authors did not undertake to find out the exact position to which the sulphonic acid group entered the nucleus. Hence the nomenclature used throughout was a general one, without assigning any restricted position to any group.

The compounds which are all yellow dissolve in alkali with a deep red colour and are precipitated by acids. The compounds were crystallised from glacial acetic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Coumarin-6-azonaphthylsulphoarsinic acid.— Naphthylsulphoarsinic acid (4 g.) was dissolved by stirring in 25 p.c. solution of sodium hydroxide. To this a few c.c. more of sodium hydroxide was added and was allowed to cool to 0° in an ice-bath. 6-Aminocoumarin (2 g.) was dissolved in a solution of hydrochloric acid (1 c.c. in 8 c.c. water). The solution was heated and then filtered hot to free it from insoluble matters. The filtrate was cooled to 0° and to this powdered ice was added. The well-cooled solution was next diazotised with a solution of sodium nitrite (0.4 g. in 5 c.c. water). The resulting diazo solution was added with constant stirring to the alkaline solution of the sulphoarsinic acid kept at 0°. The whole was allowed to stand overnight and then filtered. The red solution was acidified with hydrochloric acid, which gave a yellow precipitate. This was separated, dried and then recrystallised from acetic acid in a yellow microcrystalline product, m.p. 185° (decomp.). The acid is insoluble in water but dissolves readily in caustic alkalis and alkaline carbonates. (Found: N, 5.45; As, 14.76. $C_{19}H_{13}O_8N_2SAs$ requires N, 5.55; As, 14.88 per cent.)

7-Methylcoumarin-6-azonaphthylsulphoarsinic acid.— This was prepared in a similar way from 7-methyl-6-aminocoumarin as the previous one. The only precaution that was necessary was that the acid solution of the amino compound was treated with excess of pounded ice and the nitrite solution was added all at once. The compound was precipitated as a dark brown mass as before with hydrochloric acid and was recrystallised from acetic acid in yellow powder. It shrinks at 169° and decomposes at 235°. (Found: N, 5.30; As, 14.2. $C_{20}H_{15}O_8N_2SAs$ requires N, 5.4; As, 14.4 per cent.)

4:7-Dimethylcoumarin-6-azonaphthylsulphoarsinic acid, prepared in a similar manner from 4 : 7-dimethyl-6-aminocoumarin and naphthylsulphoarsinic acid, recrystallised from acetic acid in yellow microcrystalline powder, m.p. 204° (decomp.). (Found : N, 5.18 ; As, 13.85. $C_{21}H_{17}O_8N_2$ SAs requires N, 5.2 ; As 14.09 per cent.).

1 : 2- α -Naphthapyrone-6-azonaphthylsulphoarsinic acid was prepared in a similar way from 6-amino-1 : 2 α -naphthapyrone and naphthylsulphoarsinic acid. The only modification that was necessary was that the diazotised solution was filtered cold before coupling. The compound was crystallised from acetic acid to a mass of yellow microcrystalline powder shrinking at 170°. (Found : N, 4.7 ; As, 12.98. $C_{23}H_{15}O_8N_2$ SAs requires N, 5.05 ; As, 13.53 per cent.).

4-Methyl-1 : 2- α -naphthapyrone-6-azonaphthylsulphoarsinic acid.—The method of preparation of this compound is the same as the previous compounds. But as the hydrochloride of the base is sparingly soluble in water the diazotisation was effected in presence of excess of ice in suspended solution. The compound was crystallised from acetic acid in yellow powder, m.p. 162° (decomp.). (Found : N, 4.6 ; As, 13.1. $C_{24}H_{17}O_8N_2$ SAs requires N, 4.9 ; As, 13.2 per cent.).

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